

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Prevalence of internet addiction and its impact on socio educational area among students of selected high schools at urban areas of Davangere, Karnataka

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Abstract

Background: The Internet has developed into one of man's most important tools for information, employment possibilities, education, entertainment, social media, and networking, and it is progressively becoming an integral part of our daily lives.

Objectives: To assess prevalence of internet addiction and its impact on socio educational area among students at selected high schools of urban areas of Davangere.

Methodology: A quantitative approach with descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The samples from the selected high schools of urban areas were selected using probability multistage random sampling technique. The sample consisted of 200 high school students. A Internet addiction test developed by Dr. Young was used to measure the internet addiction and questionnaire on Impact of internet addiction on socio educational area was used to measure impact.

Results: The study result reveal that, internet addiction mean internet addiction score was 34.24, median was 34.50, mode was 25, standard deviation 11.95 and range score was 1-75. Majority 82(41%) were not had internet addiction, 83(41.5%) were had mild addiction and least 35(17.5%) of participant was had moderate level of internet addiction. With respect to impact of internet addiction on socio educational area, majority 48(43.63%) were had mild impact, 38(34.54%) were had moderate impacts and least 32(29.09%) of participants were not had impact on socio educational area. The levels of internet addiction of participants of urban area are found to be statistically significant at 0.05 levels for gender, occupation of mothers and time spent daily on internet

Conclusion: The study can help policymakers to understand the burden of internet addiction among adolescent students and can make necessary changes in the education system.

Keywords: Prevalence; Internet Addiction; Students; Urban Area; High School

1. Introduction

The Internet has developed into one of man's most important tools for information, employment possibilities, education, entertainment, social media, and networking, and it is progressively becoming an integral part of our daily

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lives. With the introduction of modern smartphones, tablets, and PCs, the general public may now easily access the Internet or have it "at their fingertips."¹

The Internet has evolved into a limitless place for social networking, information exchange, and the growth of cyber habits. It is no longer just an infrastructure.² A wide range of electronic and optical networking technologies connect the various private, public, academic, business, and government networks, which range in size from local to worldwide. Because of the internet, the world has become smaller and more resembles a little hamlet.³

By facilitating numerous types of interpersonal contact, like e-mail, instant messaging, video conferencing, and social networking, it has brought individuals closer together. The majority of us now find it challenging to envision a world without instantaneous, constant access to the internet.⁴

The Internet is a global network of linked computer networks that uses the open Internet Protocol to connect users all over the world. It transports a large array of information services and resources, including the World Wide Web's (WWW) hypertext content and the infrastructure necessary to enable electronic mail.⁵

Due to online studies and their innate propensity to use the internet, adolescents' addiction sensitivity seems to be a more significant issue than it is for adults. As a result, there has been an increase in linked psychopathology, academic decline, and maladaptive behaviour patterns.⁶

By becoming a part of our daily lives, the Internet has changed and enhanced many parts of our life alongside new technologies. Every age group is using the internet more frequently as it has expanded in availability, features, and usability. Today, 46% of the world's population uses the Internet, a remarkable increase from fewer than 1% in 1995. The world's most developed nations, such as Iceland, Norway, Denmark, UK, or Japan, already have an Internet penetration rate of over 90%, but developing nations on the African continent, such as Mali, Cameroon, and Côte d'Ivoire, have the fastest growth rates. Croatia has 75% of the European average with a rate of 73, 5% of which utilise the internet.⁷

Prevention is always preferable to treatment. By educating, screening, identifying, and modifying risk factors, one strategy to decrease the prevalence of internet addiction in adolescents is to increase their adherence to healthy lifestyles. A poor level of health and several health issues may be the result of ignorance and carelessness.

The early detection and prevention of diseases is one of the nurse's key responsibilities. The researcher was motivated to take on this subject for investigation by taking into account all of the aforementioned criteria.

Objectives

- To assess prevalence of internet addiction among students at selected high schools of Davangere
- To find out impact of internet addiction on socio-educational areas of students at selected high schools of Davangere
- To find out the association of Internet addiction among students of selected high schools and their selected sociodemographic variables.

1.1. Hypothesis

H₀₃: There will be significant association between the prevalence of internet addiction scores among students of selected high school and their selected socio demographic variables at 0.05 level of significance

2. Methodology

- Research Approach: Quantitative evaluative Research Approach
- Research Design : Descriptive survey design
- Sampling technique: Probability multistage random Sampling Technique
- Sample size: 200
- Setting of study: High schools of urban areas of Davangere
- Method of data collection: Questionnaire

2.1. Tools used

- Section I : Socio-demographic variables of Participants
- Section II : Youngs Internet addiction test
- Section III : Questionnaire on Impact of internet addiction on socio educational area

Internet addiction test developed by Dr. Young was used to measure the internet addiction among high school students. A structured internet addiction test scale consisted of 20 statements regarding individual's pattern of use of internet. There are six alternative response columns; rarely, occasionally, frequently, often, always and do not apply. There was no right or wrong answers and respondents were asked to express their opinion honestly. Total internet addiction test scale scores ranged from 0-100 and internet addiction on the bases of score obtained are again divided in to three categories as follows-

2.2. Scoring Keys

- Total score: 0-100
- Mild addiction: 31-49points
- Moderate addiction: 50-79 points
- Sever addiction: 80-100 points
- Section III: Impact of internet addiction on socio educational area

“Impact of internet addiction on socio educational area scale” is a 6-item scale used to estimate the impacts of internet addiction on socio educational area of the participants. There were two alternative answers as Yes or No. The participant has to choose one answer from given options based on problems they are experiencing due to internet addiction. The option Yes will be scored as 'one' mark and the option No will be scored as 'zero' comprising the maximum score of 0-6. The impacts of internet addiction on the bases of score obtained are again divided in to three categories as follows.

2.3. Levels of Impact

- Mild impact: 0-2
- Moderate impact: 3-4
- Severe impact: 5-6

2.4. Procedure of data collection

High schools from urban areas of Davangere district were selected as per sampling plan. Number of participants from each selected institution was predetermined while making the sampling plan. After making list of participants from each educational institutions, required samples were drawn from the available list according to sampling plan. Written consent for involvement in research project has been taken from each sample and their parents by clarifying their doubts.all the participants given their genuine responses for each question asked to them and at the same time their doubts regarding questions were cleared by researcher.

3. Results

3.1. The findings related to socio-demographic variables of participants

The sample consisted of adolescents in the age range of 13 to 16 years old, majority 63(31.5%) of participants were belonged to 15 years. Majority 134(67%) of participants were females. With regard to class of studying, majority 88(44%) were studying in 10th standard. Majority of participants 154(77%) were belonged to Hindu religion. Majority 77(38.5%) of participants were had income of Rs.10,000-20,000. With regard to education of fathers and mother of participants majority of participants fathers and mothers were had secondary school education, majority of participants fathers were doing business, majority of participants mothers were home makers, majority of participants are using internet by mobiles, spending less than one hour for internet daily and using internet for study purposes and participants were had previous knowledge regarding internet use.

3.1.1. Description of prevalence of internet addiction among participants

I: Description of mean, median, mode, standard deviation and range internet addiction scores of participants

Table 1 Distribution of internet addiction scores n = 200

Mean	Median	Mode	Sd	Range
34.24	34.50	25	11.95	1-75

Participants mean internet addiction score was 34.24, median was 34.50, mode was 25, standard deviation 11.95 and range score was 1-75.

3.1.2. Description of findings related to level internet addiction among participants

Table 2 Frequency and Percentage distribution of respondents according to level of internet addiction n = 200

Level of Internet addiction			
No addiction	Mild	Moderate	Severe
f (%)	f (%)	f (%)	f (%)
82 (41%)	83 (41.5%)	35 (17.5%)	00

Among the participants, majority 82(41%) were not had internet addiction, 83(41.5%) were had mild addiction and least 35(17.5%) of participant was had moderate level of internet addiction.

Figure 1 Frequency and percentage distribution of participants according to their levels of internet addiction

3.1.3. Findings related to impact of internet addiction on socio educational area

Table 3 Socio-Educational Problems due to internet addiction among participants N= 118

Sl. No	Socio-Educational Problems due to internet addiction	f	%
1	I am facing problem in maintaining social relationship	14	12.72
2	I am facing problem in my academic performance	43	39.09
3	My family is facing problem of financial burdens	09	8.18
4	I am not able to concentrate in class	34	30.90
5	I am not interested in outdoor activities	13	11.81
6	I am facing problem in my family relationship	29	26.36

Above table depicts the socio educational problems faced by participants due to internet addiction, it reveals that, majority 43(39.09%) of participants were facing the problem related to academic performance, 34(30.90%) were not able to concentrate on class, 29(36.36%) were facing problem in maintaining family relationship, 14(12.72%) were

facing the problem of social relationship, 13(11.81%) were not interested in outdoor activities and 9(8.18%) were facing the financial burdens.

Table 4 Frequency and Percentage distribution of respondents according to level of impact of internet addiction on socio educational area = 118

Level of impact of Internet addiction on socio educational area			
No impact	Mild	Moderate	Severe
f (%)	f (%)	f (%)	f (%)
32(29.09%)	48(43.63)	38(34.54)	00

Above table depicts that, majority 48(43.63%) were had mild impact, 38(34.54%) were had moderate impacts and least 32(29.09%) of participants were not had impact on socio educational area.

3.1.4. Findings related to association between levels of internet addition and selected socio demographic variables

Table 5 Association between selected demographic variables and levels of internet addiction among participants of urban area= 200

Sl No	Demographic variables	Levels of addiction			Chi square value	P value
		No addiction	Mild	Moderate		
1.	Year of study				13.78	0.03
	8 th std	18	34	7		
	9 th std	24	17	11		
	10 th std	40	32	17		
2.	Education of father				18.26	0.05
	Illiterate	3	7	0		
	Primary edn	17	8	10		
	Higher primary	17	21	2		
	Secondary	20	23	14		
	Graduation	18	20	6		
	PG and above	7	4	3		
3.	Time spent daily on internet				37.01	0.001
	Less than 1 hour					
	1-2 hours	59	37	8		
	2-3 hours	18	31	21		
	More than 3 hours	3	13	2		
4.	Previous knowledge				7.66	0.02
	Yes	58	50	30		
	No	24	33	5		
5.	Source of knowledge				23.91	0.008
	Formal edn	15	13	16		
	Books /News paper	25	10	3		
	Mass media	13	21	9		
	Seminar/ workshop	4	3	1		
	Others	0	0	1		

The computed Chi-square value for association between levels of internet addiction of participants of urban area is found to be statistically significant at 0.05 levels for year of study, education of father, time spent daily on internet, previous knowledge and sources of knowledge where as it is not found significant for other selected socio demographic variables at 0.05 levels.

4. Discussion

Study findings are similar with the other study conducted among Teenagers from five Vadodara-area schools in grades 8 through 11 were chosen for the study. According to the study's findings, 724 participants who successfully completed the IAT were examined. 98.9% of people reported using the internet. There were 8.7% IA cases. In order to determine the prevalence of Internet use and Internet addiction among schoolchildren in the Municipality of Novi Sad, Serbia, aged 14 to 18, revealed that, out of 553 participants, 62.7% of women and an average age of 15.6 years were present. 400 high school pupils and 153 students in primary school made up the sample. A cross-sectional survey conducted among 300 students in three private schools in the city of Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh revealed that, 61.34% students started using internet after 12 yrs of age while 38.66% students said that they started using internet before 12 year of age. 26.33% students spent 4 hour or more online per day.

5. Conclusion

The study findings can help policymakers to understand the burden of internet addiction among adolescent students and can make necessary changes in the education system. To provide evidence for the intervention programs related to internet addiction in preventing bio-psycho-social problems and promoting adolescent bio-psycho-social health.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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